

**Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for
smaller enterprises in Europe**

D7.5 - Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report - interim version

This work is part of the SENTINEL project. SENTINEL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Work Programme for research and innovation 2018-2020 under grant agreement n°101021659.

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101021659
Project Acronym	SENTINEL
Project Full Title	Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe
Starting Date	1 st June 2021
Duration	36 months
Call Identifier	H2020-SU-DS-2020
Topic	H2020-SU-DS-2018-2019-2020 Digital Security and privacy for citizens and Small and Medium Enterprises and Micro Enterprises
Project Website	https://www.sentinel-project.eu/
Project Coordinator	Dr. George Bravos
Organisation	Information Technology for Market Leadership (ITML)
Email	gebravos@itml.gr

Document Information

Work Package	Work Package - 7
Deliverable Title	D7.5- Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report - interim version
Version	1.6
Date of Submission	24/11/2022
Main Editor(s)	Ruben Costa (UNINOVA), Cláudio Côrrea (UNINOVA)
Contributor(s)	-
Reviewer(s)	Natalia Christofi (FP), Dimitra Malandraki (CECL), Siranush Akarmazyan (ITML)

Document Classification							
Draft		Final	X	Confidential		Public	X

History			
Version	Issue Date	Status	Distribution
1.0	15/09/2022	TOC preparation	Confidential
1.1	03/11/2022	Draft ready	Confidential
1.2	10/11/2022	1 st review by FP	Confidential
1.3	10/11/2022	2 nd Draft ready	Confidential
1.4	15/11/2022	2 nd review by CECL	Confidential
1.5	22/11/2022	3 rd review by ITML	Confidential
1.6	23/11/2022	Final version ready	Public

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	3
List of Figures.....	4
Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	7
1.2 Structure of the document.....	8
1.3 Intended readership	8
2. SENTINEL Ecosystem Building and SMEs Engagement Strategy	9
2.1 Objectives.....	9
2.2 Ecosystem building phases	9
2.3 SMEs analysis and mapping.....	9
2.4 SME engagement methods	10
2.5 Stakeholder engagement time plan	10
3. SENTINEL’s SME’s Engagement Activities	11
3.1 1st SME-centric workshop	11
3.2 2nd SME-centric workshop.....	12
3.3 3rd SME-centric workshop.....	12
4. First Insights from the SENTINEL’s SME’s Engagement Activities.....	13
4.1 Analysis of the 1st SMEs engagement questionnaire.....	13
4.2 Analysis of the 2nd SMEs engagement questionnaire.....	23
4.3 Analysis of the 3rd SMEs engagement questionnaire	29
5. Conclusion and Future Steps	37

List of Figures

Figure 1. Stakeholder Engagement Time Plan	10
Figure 2. 1 st SME-centric workshop.....	12
Figure 3. 2 nd SME-centric workshop.....	12
Figure 4. 3 rd SME-centric workshop	13

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SMEs/MEs	Small, Medium Enterprises/Micro Enterprises
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OTMs	Organization and Technical Measures

Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.5 “Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – interim version” is produced within Work Package 7 (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) of the SENTINEL Project, under Task 7.4 “SENTINEL ecosystem building: Continuous engagement of technology providers, SMEs/MEs”.

This document presents the efforts of the SENTINEL project, towards building a community and an ecosystem around the project’s results. The report presented, establishes a solid SENTINEL stakeholder engagement strategy and time plan to outline the stakeholder communication activities for the entire project period. In particular, it includes a first step towards the networking and liaisons with technical- and domain-specific communities. Furthermore, it describes the activities organized for potential end-users and stakeholders to promote the project’s technologies and impact assessment outcomes for future transferability to other domains and thus sustainability. As part of this strategy and aiming to trigger an interest of primary stakeholders, first insights from the stakeholder analysis are illustrated in this report based on the 1st, 2nd and 3rd stakeholder engagement questionnaires released according to the stakeholder engagement plan.

This document aims at reporting the activities carried out during the first 18 months of the project, within Task 7.4. This follows SENTINEL Dissemination Strategy in which the SENTINEL stakeholders’ engagement activities are to be reported. This deliverable will be updated in month 36 as per deliverable D7.6 “Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – final version”.

1. Introduction

Over 25 million European SMEs/MEs, central within EU enterprise policy, face multiple challenges related to personal data protection; ranging from awareness to a clear and practical roadmap to compliance, the most prominent one is the fact that, unlike larger enterprises, SMEs/MEs lack access to enterprise-grade cybersecurity technology and capacity-building for compliance, making them increasingly often victims of costly data breaches. SENTINEL aspires to bridge this gap by boosting SMEs/MEs capabilities in this domain through innovation at a cost-effective level. SENTINEL will integrate tried and tested modular cybersecurity technologies including new ones, such as a novel Identity Management System for human-centric data portability towards enabling a unified “European Data Space”, and an end-to-end digital personal data protection compliance self-assessment framework for SMEs, into a unified digital architecture. Data from these modules will then undergo disruptive Intelligence for Compliance through SENTINEL’s digital core, featuring machine learning-powered recommendations, policy drafting & enforcement for compliance and a ‘one-stop-shop’ incident response center.

Combined with a well-researched methodology for application, an open knowledge sharing hub and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation, SENTINEL will catalyse adoption of market-leading security tech among SMEs/MEs and help safeguard their and their customers’ assets.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – interim version (D7.5), builds a community and an ecosystem around the project’s results during the project period, including networking and liaisons with technical- and domain-specific communities. This process is split into two (2) main phases: i) engaging potential end users of the SENTINEL platform (that is, processing sensitive data or dealing with cybersecurity aspects); and ii) identifying potential technology providers to enhance the SENTINEL offerings further.

The deliverable reports and analyses the results of ecosystem building activities through the indicators of success set up in the Grant Agreement.

Work Package 7 of SENTINEL (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) focuses on ensuring that the various outcomes of the project are widely disseminated to the appropriate target group, at the appropriate time and via appropriate methods. Furthermore, it aims at identifying stakeholders who can contribute to the development, evaluation and uptake of the project outcomes and encouraged them to participate in the project’s current and future actions.

The main objectives of WP7 are:

- Develop the project’s visual identity.
- Raise awareness about the project concept, developments and findings to all key actors.
- Develop the dissemination and communication strategy of the project.
- Develop the SENTINEL business model and strategies for incentivizing/promoting project adoption.
- Create a marketing strategy that focuses on commercialization.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured in the following way:

- Section 2 describes the SENTINEL strategy followed for ecosystem building and SMEs engagement.
- Section 3 highlights all the SME's engagement activities performed until M18.
- Section 4 provides a detail description about the first insights from the SENTINEL's SME's engagement activities.
- Section 5 presents the final remarks and concludes the document.

1.3 Intended readership

This document is intended for both consortium members and external to the project stakeholders, by illustrating the SENTINEL strategy and the stakeholder engagement activities performed within the first 18 months of the project.

2. SENTINEL Ecosystem Building and SMEs Engagement Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The SENTINEL ecosystem building and SMEs engagement, focus on building a community and an ecosystem around the project's results. This work includes networking and liaisons with technical- and domain-specific communities, focusing on potential end-users and interested stakeholders to promote the project's technologies and impact assessment outcomes for future transferability to other domains and thus sustainability. Towards this direction, special focus has been given on Digital Innovation Hubs. Based on UNINOVA's direct involvement with in NOVA4TECH hub and other hubs, and also their strong connection with Madan Parque incubator, this task formed a solid basis for the SENTINEL ecosystem in two directions: First, by engaging with potential end users of the SENTINEL platform (that is, SMEs/MEs processing sensitive data or dealing with cybersecurity aspects); Second, by identifying potential technology providers to further and continuously enhance the SENTINEL offerings. This also includes networking with relevant associations, liaising with standardisation bodies, organizing stakeholders' workshops, linking with other H2020 projects, participating in conferences, fairs and exhibition.

2.2 Ecosystem building phases

The SENTINEL ecosystem building process is divided into 3 main phases: (i) Networking and Liaison; (ii) Sustainability building; and (iii) Market outreach.

The first phase "Networking and Liaison", started at M1 and finished at M12. This phase is related to the organization of workshops for engaging stakeholders, starting to liaise with other H2020 projects, start defining what are the project main offerings and also the production of stakeholder questionnaires.

The second phase "Sustainability building", started at M13 and will finish at M24. The main objectives are to analyse the results from previous phase, to set a clear definition of the SENTINEL offerings and value proposition, to boost the engagement with key stakeholders through workshops and questionnaires.

The third and last phase "Market outreach", will start at M25 and will finish at M36. The main objectives here are to study the early adopters per use case and organize early-adopters targeted events.

2.3 SMEs analysis and mapping

In order to start the stakeholder engagement activities, the SENTINEL consortium has organized three SME-centric workshops, as well as a Webinar on "A privacidade e a proteção de dados pessoais no panorama nacional das PMEs" (Privacy and Personal Data Protection in the current SME landscape), which accounted more than 100 attendees in total, including SMEs/MEs coming from different domain areas and countries across the EU. The first objective was to raise awareness of SENTINEL offerings and engage SMEs as future end users of SENTINEL services. The workshops were accompanied by a questionnaire that helped the consortium better understand the SMEs' needs, challenges, current OTMs, infrastructure and awareness of

GDPR compliance obligations. SENTINEL has also engaged different DIHs, at national and EU level.

SENTINEL was present at the “Transferable Research & Laboratory Outcome” held on the 29th of April, UNINOVA, Lisbon, Portugal. In this event, there was a presentation of SENTINEL in one of the tracks dedicated to DIHs. During this event we have received an expression of interest from the “Digital Manufacturing Innovation Hub Wales”, to collaborate with SENTINEL, in order to test and validate our offerings.

The aim is to continue with such activities to address a much wider network. Additional DIHs have been already identified and interactions are being made for promoting SENTINEL in such ecosystems. SENTINEL is planning to engage with the European catalogue of DIHs, launched by the European Commission. It is an online repository that includes more than 1.000 existing hubs across Europe. The plan is to use this network to disseminate SENTINEL offerings, promote events and liaise with different DIHs. SENTINEL has also initiated preliminary contacts with the following DIHs: INNOVA4TECH, Digital Manufacturing Innovation of Wales, INNOV TOURISM DIH, idD Portugal Defense, CONNECT5 and Madeira Digital Innovation Hub.

2.4 SME engagement methods

For initial SME engagement activities, SENTINEL focused on collecting data to profile the context of SMEs and to understand the gaps related to non-compliance with GDPR and mechanisms for addressing personal data protection. For the 1st and 2nd SME engagement workshops, the questionnaires used to collect data were sent after workshops while for the 3rd workshop the feedback was collected through a live survey campaign facilitated via a QR code.

The main objective of organizing such workshops and webinars was to listen to SMEs themselves, start the discussions around cybersecurity and demystify GDPR compliance obligations. To fulfill such objectives and have substantial impact on SMEs, SENTINEL has also launched a podcast initiative where people from different countries from the cybersecurity and personal data protection domain, are invited to short conversation, in order to reveal their opinion about the *status quo* of SMEs nowadays, what are the common threats, and also how can SMEs move forward towards GDPR compliance and personal data protection.

2.5 Stakeholder engagement time plan

The SENTINEL stakeholder engagement time plan methodology consists of four phases (shown in Figure 8) which are aligned with the SENTINEL overall methodology and time-plan.

Figure 1. Stakeholder Engagement Time Plan

The Baseline Phase (M1-M6) is where SENTINEL triggered awareness within SMEs about SENTINEL’s motivations, objectives and offerings. The 1st SME-centric workshop was held at M4,

where SENTINEL was presented to a manufacturing ecosystem of SMEs. In this workshop a consultation to the SMEs present at the workshop was held through questionnaires, with the objective of understating the level of maturity of SMEs with regards to GDPR and PDP compliance and also, the usage of cybersecurity tools.

The Innovation Phase (M7-M18) comprehends the period related with the technical development of the SENTINEL's MVP. In this phase, two (2) more SME-centric workshops were organized, one at M12 and another one at M17, in this last one, a preview of SENTINEL's MVP hands-on was presented. During the workshop, a questionnaire was addressed to all attendees, aiming to consolidate reviews about the first impression of SENTINEL's MVP. Besides the 2 SME-centric workshops organized, also webinars and attendance at recognized events (e.g., IoT week, FIC Forum) had taken place. Such dissemination events, where also good opportunities to engage different SMEs to SENTINEL's offerings.

The Demonstration Phase (M19-M30) will have a strong focus on dissemination and communication activities, aiming to enlarge the number of SMEs engaged with SENTINEL's offering. These activities will also address different DIHs and incubators, that will facilitate raising awareness among SMEs. Such activities (e.g., workshops, open demonstrations, webinars and seminars) will promote the SENTINEL platform and its offerings to all stakeholders, focusing mainly on SMEs/MEs operating on any field related with needs on data privacy and compliance, technology providers, and policy makers. All members of the consortium will be engaged in promoting these events in industrial and scientific communities (via their web-based dissemination channels) and inviting participants.

The Consolidation & Sustainability Management Phase (M31-M36) will focus on fine tuning the SENTINEL platform, on completing its set of features and fixing any defects identified through the pilots' execution in order to come up with an almost ready-for-market offering. A sound business plan that will ensure the platform's sustainability will be released at the end of this phase.

The Consolidation & Sustainability Management Phase (M31-M36) will focus on design and describe the best practices for maintaining and operating the system in the long-term. This will include, collecting feedback from SMEs regarding the final SENTINEL platform but also to create adequate support channels to SMEs which are interested to adopt SENTINEL platform in a long-term, this will include, the production of a well-documented end-user guide for installing, deploying and using the SENTINEL and its components. Moreover, this phase will attempt to validate the utility of the proposed solution at a larger scale, within wider European business community.

3. SENTINEL's SME's Engagement Activities

3.1 1st SME-centric workshop

The first SME engagement workshop took place in Guimarães, Portugal, on the 16th of September 2021. Due to COVID-19 strict restrictions, participants reached 10+ attendees. Within this workshop, a first presentation about the SENTINEL objectives and motivations was given, followed by an interactive discussion between participants and the SENTINEL consortium, represented by the project coordinator Dr. George Bravos (ITML). Apart from disseminating SENTINEL and starting to create awareness among SMEs, the objective of this workshop was to

have a very first understanding the context of the SMEs, regarding GDPR compliance and Personal Data Protection. At the end of the workshop, the participants were requested to fill out a questionnaire, in order to access their internal practices into what concerns GDPR, Personal Data Protection and Cybersecurity. The results of the questionnaire can be found in Section 4.1.

Figure 2. 1st SME-centric workshop

3.2 2nd SME-centric workshop

The second workshop was held in M12 (6th of May 2022), focusing on understanding the scenario and levels of knowledge around GDPR and Cybersecurity inside companies. For this second event, SENTINEL addressed the topics: internal processes, data management, profiling company, business plans with SENTINEL inside companies, and plans for GDPR and Cyber Security. Although the second workshop was intended to be a hybrid event, all the participant companies (mainly from Greece) joined the event remotely. The results of the questionnaire can be found in Section 4.2.

Figure 3. 2nd SME-centric workshop

3.3 3rd SME-centric workshop

The third SME-centric workshop and the last one before M18 was held on the 24th of October 2022 co-located with the Digital Summit event, organized by UNINOVA, which took place in Funchal, Madeira. We have received more than 100 registrations for the workshop, which accounted with more than 70 people attending physically. During the workshop, participants had the chance to participate in our SME questionnaire, where we were able to collect 52 responses.

The focus of the 3rd SME-centric workshop was to present the SENTINEL project to regional SMEs from Madeira Island, but also to have a first glimpse of the SENTINEL MVP features and look and feel. The idea was to have a first contact with the SMEs regarding MVP usability, UI and UX. The results of the questionnaire can be found in Section 4.3.

Figure 4. 3rd SME-centric workshop

4. First Insights from the SENTINEL’s SME’s Engagement Activities

Aiming at attracting end-users to the SENTINEL platform and its toolkits and creating mutual beneficial synergies with them by strengthening further project’s commercial links multiple questionnaires have been prepared in order to collect and reveal the main challenges and needs of the SENTINEL stakeholders. These questionnaires are analysed and accessed beyond this document.

4.1 Analysis of the 1st SMEs engagement questionnaire

As previously mentioned, the 1st SME engagement workshop was held in Guimarães, Portugal. Guimaraes is a city, located in the north of Portugal, close to the Vale do Ave region.

The industry in Vale do Ave appears in 1845 with a first factory, the “*Fiação e Tecidos*” (Spinning and Fabrics) from Rio Vizela (Vizela river), in Santo Tirso. In the second half of the 19th century, more and more companies were emerged and reached almost two hundred. Nowadays, there are not so many, but the territory continues to have a strong industrial presence, with manufacturing units that merge into the rural landscape of the periphery, fixed on the banks of the Ave River or its tributaries and that go far beyond textiles. Tires, shoes, cameras and lenses, cookies and even chocolates are made in these lands.

Due to Vale do Ave region’s characteristics, we believe that this location could be a good option to start awareness raising on the SENTINEL objectives, among the industries located in Vale do Ave.

Overall, 11 responses were achieved as a result of the 1st SME engagement questionnaire. The insights of the questionnaire can be summarized as follows:

- The participating companies have more than 50 employees and more than 40% work in the technology area.
- Most companies are aware that they process personal data.
- The sectors that most process personal data are product sales and research.
- Most personal data in companies is related to customer and employee data. Even if to a lesser extent, companies also process supplier data.
- Most use HR systems to manage personal data and manage payments.
- In general, companies have basic knowledge of GDPR. And 34% of the participating companies showed not having or not knowing whether they have internal security policies or cyber-attack response protocols.

Even technology companies, aware of the GDPR, do not have protocols or processes aimed at the security of personal data, mainly dedicated to the protection of employee data. More than 60% of participating companies are developing measures to increase cybersecurity and data protection, including internal employee training.

A more detailed overview of the questionnaire answers can be found below.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1-10 0 ● 11-49 0 ● 50-100 5 ● >100 6 	
<p>3. How would you rate your understanding of the concept of personal data?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - Not at all 0 ● 2 - A little 1 ● 3 - Basic 3 ● 4 - Very well 6 ● 5 - We are experts 1 	
<p>4. Does your company process personal data?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 10 ● No 1 ● I am not sure 0 	
<p>5. What types of data processing activities do you carry out?</p>	

6. Which company's functions process personal data?

7. Who are your data subjects (e.g. Data subject refers to any individual person who can be identified, directly or indirectly, via an identifier such as a name, an ID number, location data, or via factors specific to the person's physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity)?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Staff 8 ● Customers 8 ● Suppliers 3 ● Business partners 2 ● Outro 3 	
<p>8. How aware are you of your obligations under GDPR and the lawful basis on which you collect and process personal data?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - Not at all 2 ● 2 - A little 1 ● 3 - Basic 4 ● 4 - Very well 4 ● 5 - We are experts 0 	
<p>9. How would you rate your company's overall compliance with the GDPR?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 - Non-compliant 0 ● 2 - Poor 2 ● 3 - Fair 5 ● 4 - Good 3 ● 5 - Excellent (fully compliant) 1 	
<p>10. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Right of Access? (e.g. data subjects can access their data free of charge, along with the technical means to isolate this information from other personal data)</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 7 ● No 3 ● I don't know how to answer this question 1 	
<p>11. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Right of Rectification? (e.g., possess the technical means, trained staff and processes to rectify inaccurate data without undue delay)</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 8 ● No 3 ● I don't know how to answer this question 0 	
<p>12. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Right of Erasure? (e.g., possess the technical means, trained staff and processes to locate and totally erase all instances of a person's data – and prove that you have done so)</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 7 ● No 3 ● I don't know how to answer this question 1 	
<p>13. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Right of Restrict Processing? (e.g., possess the technical means, trained staff and processes to protect specific or datasets from being used or processed)</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 5 ● No 5 ● I don't know how to answer this question 1 	
<p>14. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Right of Object? (e.g., possess the technical means, trained staff and processes to isolate, extract or remove from active processing a requester's personal data, across the entire company)</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 6 ● No 4 ● I don't know how to answer this question 1 	
<p>15. Do you have the means to comply with individuals' Rights related to automated decision-making including profiling? (e.g., are you able to substitute automated decision-making with a manual process, for multiple data subjects, and are able to prove this)</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 1 ● No 3 ● Does not apply 6 ● I don't know how to answer this question 1 	
<p>16. Do you process personal data over the Internet?</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No 4 ● Yes, over the Cloud applications (e.g., CRM) 6 ● Yes, over Cloud services like Dropbox 4 ● Yes, we sell products or services online 1 	
<p>17. Do employees have access to your IT assets via the Internet (e.g., via VPN)?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 7 ● No 4 	
<p>18. Are your IT systems for personal data processing connected to external services (e.g., third parties, Cloud providers etc)?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes 8 ● No 3 	
<p>19. Have you taken specific measures to prevent unauthorized people from accessing your data processing environment?</p>	

<p>● Yes 7 ● No 4</p>	
<p>20. Does the data you (or your assigned third parties) process involve Personally Identifiable Information (PII)? PII is data that can be used to clearly identify an individual. E.g. name, national insurance number, physical address, email address, phone number, financial data, IP address, login details, social media activity, digital images, geolocation data, behavioural data, medical data, biometric data, customer purchase & loyalty history.</p>	
<p>● Yes 7 ● No 4</p>	
<p>21. Is your HR aware that employees are data subjects too and that GDPR applies to the processing of employee data?</p>	
<p>● Yes 7 ● No 4</p>	
<p>22. Select the systems you might be using that are used in the processing of personal data</p>	

23. Do you have an internal security policy / Would you be able to document that you have taken measures to protect personal data from external and internal threats?

24. Have you taken measures to encrypt, pseudonymize, or anonymize personal data?

25. Does your company have an incident (security or data breach) response protocol?

<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Yes 6● No 5	
<p>26. Are you recording and managing consent for processing personal data?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Yes 7● No 4	
<p>27. Are you taking steps to foster awareness for cybersecurity and personal data protection among staff (e.g., training)?</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Yes 8● No 3	

4.2 Analysis of the 2nd SMEs engagement questionnaire

As mentioned in Section 3.2 the 2nd SME-centric workshop took place on the 6th of May 2022 and gathered mainly Greek companies who joined the event remotely. The workshop was organized

by SENTINEL incorporation with the PRAXI Network¹. The event consisted with the following three parts.

In the first part, a presentation of the SENTINEL project was given. In this respect, the project's main offerings, its innovation capacities and how an SME can utilize them were presented.

This was followed by an open discussion on focus topics, with companies being able to ask their questions and share their concerns about GDPR, personal data protection and cybersecurity.

In the third part of the event, the participants were invited to express their thoughts and concerns about privacy issues, as well as their willingness to trial the SENTINEL framework as end-users via the 2nd SMEs engagement questionnaire. Overall, 4 responses were achieved as a result of the 2nd SMEs engagement questionnaire. Some important insights are presented below:

- All participating companies are from the technology and engineering area with 11 to 49 employees. They are somewhat or quite aware of GDPR obligations and claim to process personal data.
- The areas of companies that most process personal data are Sales, Marketing and HR. Consequently, the data is related to consumers/clients and employees.
- 75% say that the data collected contains personally identifiable information, the other 25% do not know.
- Only 50% of companies say they have the means to guarantee the Right to access and rectify data according to GDPR, 25% do not know how to inform and 25% say they do not have the means.

The processing of employee and customer data continues to be one of the major data processing activities of the participating companies. One of the problems addressed was the issue of identifiable personal data without encryption for protection and half of the companies do not know or say that there are no means of guaranteeing the Right to Access and Rectification of data according to GDPR, thus creating an alert in this topic.

A more detailed overview on the SMEs answers can be found below.

¹ <https://praxinetwork.gr/en/home/>

Do the data you (or your assigned third parties) process involve Personally Identifiable Information (PII)? PII is data that can be used to clearly identify...biometric data, customer purchase & loyalty history
4 respostas

Is your HR aware that employees are data subjects too and that GDPR applies to the processing of employee data?
4 respostas

4.3 Analysis of the 3rd SMEs engagement questionnaire

As described in Section 3.3 the SENTINEL project was promoted during the Digital Transformation Summit ² event, via a dedicated interactive workshop session executed on the 25th of October 2022. This session was moderated by the SENTINEL Dissemination Manager, with an active performance of the Project Coordinator and the Scientific and Technical Manager. In this regard, Dr. George Bravos has presented the SENTINEL project while Dr. Manolis Falelakis has successfully demonstrated the SENTINEL MVP. Overall, the workshop was gathered more than 70 attendees from different SMEs and Academic institutions and we had the chance to communicate with external audiences, engage with potential end-users as well as collect their feedback through a live survey campaign facilitated via a QR code. Overall, 52 responses were achieved as a result of the 3rd SMEs engagement questionnaire.

² <https://summit.digit-madeira.pt/>

Some important insights are presented below:

- More than 50% of the people attending the workshop were looking for data protection and cybersecurity solutions or getting a deeper understanding about such concepts.
- The majority of the participants stated that they accept cookies on websites. This can be suggesting that people are not aware of how vulnerable their personal data is over the internet. This contrasts with the 75% of responses saying that they don't feel safe when filling personal data online.
- Regarding the background of the attendees, the majority (62%) are from the technology and engineering sectors. 67% said that their companies handle personal data, and the rest, mention that their companies don't handle personal data or don't know how to answer. 48% of the responders, acknowledge that they are not aware if they are in compliance with GDPR and data protection protocols. Only 15% of the responders claim that their companies have an incident response protocol, but 50% claim that they don't need support or advisory services, because there are already implementing measures to address GDPR compliance.
- With regards to MVP functionalities, 29% found it to be a potential solution to be implemented in their companies. 42% have answered that they could consider investing in tools/services similar to SENTINEL within the next 2 years, or 2 years after. 52% of the responders, are very likely or moderate likely to adopt SENTINEL in their own businesses.
- From the SENTINEL offerings, 54% choose "Automated GDPR compliance, recommendation and real-time monitoring" as the most useful for their own business needs.

A more detailed overview of the questionnaire answers can be found below.

If you process personal data, are you sure that you do it in compliance with GDPR regulation and data protection protocols?

■ Yes, absolutely. ■ No ■ I don't know ■ I do not process personal data)

Does your company have an incident (security or data breach) response protocol?

■ Yes ■ No ■ I don't know

Do you need support/advisory on how to comply with GDPR regulation, implement cybersecurity and data protection protocols/measures?

- Yes
- No, we are already implementing such measures with internal staff.
- No, we are using external auditing/ consultancy services.
- I don't know.

Did you find it a potential solution to be implemented within your company?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Which of the following SENTINEL offerings would be more useful for your business needs? Choose one or more

- SME Training and Education
- Evidence-based GDPR compliance
- Automated GDPR compliance, recommendation and real-time monitoring
- None-not interested

5. Conclusion and Future Steps

The objective of this deliverable is to report and analyze the results of ecosystem building activities that were undertaken in the first 18 months of project lifetime. At the end of the project, SENTINEL consortium is expected to engage with more than 8 DIHs and reach 10.000 SMEs.

Within the first 18 months of project duration, SENTINEL triggered engagement activities with four (4) different DIHs, namely, Produtech, DIH4CPS, DIHWorld and Madeira DIH. Such synergies have contributed to organization of three SME-centric workshops and participation in several webinars. The objective was to start spreading the SENTINEL's mission and main objectives across the European SMEs. During the first 12 months of project, the physical engagement with SME was relatively difficult, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The evidence of this obstacle is also visible from the number of responses gained for the 1st and 2nd questionnaires. On the contrary, the 3rd SME centric workshop managed to engage with wider audiences thanks to its physical nature.

The main insights and conclusions from the released questionnaires, validate some of the European studies which state that Millions of small businesses aren't GDPR compliant³. The analysis of the questionnaires also shows us that, apart from not being GDPR compliant, a significative percentage of the companies, are not sure if they are compliant or not, or if they will require support or legal and technical advisory to be compliant with GDPR. On the other hand, the majority of the companies are willing to use SENTINEL or similar solutions, within the 2 years' time or after 2 years.

There is still substantial work to be done, regarding building a SENTINEL ecosystem and engaging SMEs, but preliminary results regarding how SENTINEL can "bridge the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe", look promising. There is a room for creating more awareness at the SME/ME level, by educating SME on guidelines and best practices and driving this transition via the SENTINEL platform and its offerings.

³ <https://gdpr.eu/2019-small-business-survey/>